

RSS-Based Direction-of-Arrival Estimation with Increased Accuracy for Arbitrary Elevation Angles Using ESPAR Antennas

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Abstract— In this paper, we have proposed a new direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation algorithm, which uses power pattern cross-correlation (PPCC) estimator and received signal strength (RSS) values recorded at electronically steerable parasitic array radiator (ESPAR) antenna's output port, providing more accurate DoA results for unknown signals impinging the antenna. PPCC estimator provide accurate DoA estimation results for directions lying within the horizontal plane but the estimation accuracy drops for other elevation angles as the estimator relies on ESPAR antenna's radiation patterns measurements in horizontal plane only. The proposed modification allows one to measure ESPAR antenna's radiation patterns at two different elevation planes during the calibration phase, which improves PPCC-based DoA estimation algorithm's overall accuracy when signals impinging the antenna arrive from arbitrary elevation angles. The proposed algorithm have been verified during anechoic chamber measurements using our ESPAR antenna prototype.

Index Terms— *Switched-beam antenna, electronically steerable parasitic array radiator (ESPAR) antenna, direction-of-arrival (DoA), received signal strength (RSS).*

I. INTRODUCTION

Direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation plays an important role in wireless communication systems [1]-[3] and usually involves digital beamforming technique applied to signals received by antenna arrays [4]. Because, in order to provide accurate results, digital beamforming requires a number of digital signal processing (DSP) units [4]-[5], such an approach increase the costs and energy consumption associated with systems deployments.

An interesting alternative to digital beamforming employing many DSP-based processing devices requires only one DSP unit together with electronically steerable parasitic array radiator (ESPAR) antenna [6]. In such antennas, a single active element is surrounded by a number of parasitic elements that are connected to corresponding varactor diodes as variable reactances. By providing correct bias voltages to the diodes, one can easily form a radiation pattern having a directional characteristics and also change its direction. In consequence, one can estimate DoA of a signal impinging the antenna by recording received signal strength (RSS) values of the signal for different ESPAR antenna radiation patterns [6].

Further simplification of the above concept have led to more energy efficient approach [7]-[8] that can successfully be used in wireless sensor network (WSN) applications to localize WSN nodes. By introducing ESPAR antenna parasitic elements' loads in a simpler form, i.e. being close to open or short circuit, it has been possible to simplify the antenna steering circuit and still provide the required directional radiation patterns. Instead of changing bias voltages applied to varactor diodes, which in [6] required six digital-to-analog converters (DAC) within a DSP-based controller to provide six bias voltages with 12-bit resolution, one can steer the beam by changing configuration of RF switches that are connected to the required parasitic elements' loads (close to open or short circuit). Applied simplification, allows for successful integration of ESPAR antennas with WSN nodes, where inexpensive radio transceivers are commonly used [9],[10]. Such integration enhance nodes' capabilities providing RSS-based DoA estimation functionality, which allows to improve the whole network's connectivity, coverage and energy efficiency [11].

Although RSS-based DoA estimation using an ESPAR antenna can easily be done by recording received signal strength values from an unknown target during DoA estimation for different directional radiation patterns [6],[9], the concept itself relies on accurate measurements of the radiation patterns during the calibration phase. Usually, the patterns are measured in the $\theta = 90^\circ$ plane only (i.e. aligned with the horizontal plane of the antenna), which allows for accurate DoA estimation [6],[9],[10]. However, RSS-based DoA estimation is performed using the power pattern cross-correlation (PPCC) algorithm, introduced in [6], that finds the best fit between recorded RSS values and previously measured radiation patterns. Hence, one might expect that the overall accuracy of PPCC algorithm may vary for different elevation angles as the radiation pattern in the horizontal radiation can change for different elevation angles. This effect is important from a practical application perspective, however, it has not been sufficiently addressed in the available literature.

In this article, we show, how accuracy of the RSS-based DoA estimation relying on PPCC algorithm is affected during

measurements when the elevation angle of the incoming signal is not aligned with the antenna's horizontal plane, for which the calibration have been performed. Moreover, we propose a simple extension of PPCC estimator that allows one to perform calibration in two different θ planes, which, according to conducted measurements, improves the algorithm's overall accuracy when signals impinging the antenna arrive from arbitrary elevation angles.

II. ESPAR ANTENNA

The antenna design well suitable for WSN nodes having localization or DoA estimation capabilities have been proposed in [9]. This antenna has been manufactured and its applicability has been verified during DoA estimation measurements in the horizontal plane [10], so it will be used as a starting point herein. Although, the complete antenna design is available in [10], for the sake of clarity of the paper, we will briefly present the concept below.

Fig. 1. The ESPAR antenna design together with numbering of its parasitic elements and dimensions in millimeters (as proposed in [10]).

The antenna design, presented in Fig. 1, uses 1.7 mm height FR4 laminate. The single active monopole is fed by an SMA connector with the laminate's top layer metallization being its ground plane. The monopole is surrounded by twelve parasitic elements, which can be connected to the ground or opened by a NJG1681MD7 SPDT (single-pole, double-throw) switch connected to the elements' ends. Thus, antenna's configuration can be defined by its steering vector $V = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{12}]$, where v_n denotes each parasitic element's state: $v_n = 0$ for n -th parasitic element connected to the ground and 1 for opened. Because, every parasitic element connected to the ground become a reflector, while those opened become directors, by using a microcontroller, which digital output ports are connected to the switches, one can electronically change the steering vector and control ESPAR antenna's radiation pattern.

The ESPAR antenna has been simulated in FEKO electromagnetic simulation software tool at the center frequency 2.484 GHz to obtain radiation patterns in different, than $\theta = 90^\circ$, elevation planes. The simulation results, presented in Fig. 2, indicate that the patterns' shape changes

with increasing θ , which should be taken into account in the PPCC-based DoA estimation algorithm to maintain its accuracy.

Fig. 2. The ESPAR antenna's radiation patterns (in dBi) for different elevation angles. The patterns have been obtained for steering vector $V_{max}^1 = [1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]$ providing main beam's direction $\phi_{max}^1 = 90^\circ$ aligned with y axis (see text for explanations).

III. IMPROVED DIRECTION-OF-ARRIVAL ESTIMATION FOR ARBITRARY ELEVATION ANGLES

DoA estimation using PPCC algorithm, proposed in [6], relies on horizontal plane measurements of ESPAR antenna radiation patterns performed prior DoA estimations. Then, by recording RSS values of a signal impinging from an unknown direction for the radiation patterns, one can find the signal's DoA using PPCC estimator. For an ESPAR antenna with simplified beam steering [9], which has been designed for wireless sensor network (WSN) applications, the PPCC estimator takes the following form:

$$\Gamma(\varphi) = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{12} (P(V_{max}^n, \varphi) Y(V_{max}^n))}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} P(V_{max}^n, \varphi)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} Y(V_{max}^n)^2}} \quad (1)$$

where $\{P(V_{max}^1, \varphi), P(V_{max}^2, \varphi), \dots, P(V_{max}^{12}, \varphi)\}$ are ESPAR antenna's radiation pattern values measured beforehand for all

corresponding steering vectors $\{V_{max}^1, V_{max}^2, \dots, V_{max}^{12}\}$ and $\{Y(V_{max}^1), Y(V_{max}^2), \dots, Y(V_{max}^{12})\}$ are output power values recorded during the actual estimation process for a signal impinging the antenna from an unknown direction. For such estimator, the unknown DoA angle $\hat{\varphi}$ can be found by determining the highest value of $\Gamma(\varphi)$ [6], [9]:

Because ESPAR antenna's radiation pattern values are measured in the $\theta = 90^\circ$ plane only, one can expect that when the incoming signal will be impinging the antenna from other vertical directions, than $\theta = 90^\circ$, the estimation accuracy will drop as the radiation pattern values used in (1) are not the same for all vertical directions, which can be seen in Fig. 2. Therefore, for WSN setups involving differences in heights of WSN nodes installed in the environment, one can expect higher, than reported in [6] and [10], errors in DoA estimation.

In order to increase DoA estimation accuracy for elevation angles lower than $\theta = 90^\circ$, we propose to extend PPCC method. To this end, we propose to measure ESPAR antenna's radiation patterns in two elevation planes, namely $\theta_{90} = 90^\circ$ and $\theta_{45} = 45^\circ$, and define two corresponding PPCC estimators as:

$$\Gamma_{90}(\varphi) = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{12} (P_{90}(V_{max}^n, \varphi) Y(V_{max}^n))}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} P_{90}(V_{max}^n, \varphi)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} Y(V_{max}^n)^2}} \quad (2)$$

$$\Gamma_{45}(\varphi) = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{12} (P_{45}(V_{max}^n, \varphi) Y(V_{max}^n))}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} P_{45}(V_{max}^n, \varphi)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} Y(V_{max}^n)^2}} \quad (3)$$

where $\{P_{90}(V_{max}^1, \varphi), P_{90}(V_{max}^2, \varphi), \dots, P_{90}(V_{max}^{12}, \varphi)\}$ and $\{P_{45}(V_{max}^1, \varphi), P_{45}(V_{max}^2, \varphi), \dots, P_{45}(V_{max}^{12}, \varphi)\}$ are ESPAR antenna's radiation pattern values measured in $\theta_{90} = 90^\circ$ and $\theta_{45} = 45^\circ$ elevation planes for all steering vectors $\{V_{max}^1, V_{max}^2, \dots, V_{max}^{12}\}$. In order to estimate the unknown DoA angle $\hat{\varphi}$, we propose to find angles $\hat{\varphi}_{90}$ and $\hat{\varphi}_{45}$ corresponding to the maximum values of estimators $\Gamma_{90}(\varphi)$ and $\Gamma_{45}(\varphi)$ defined by (2) and (3), and then to calculate the unknown DoA using the following formulae:

$$\hat{\varphi} = \begin{cases} \hat{\varphi}_{90} & \text{if } \Gamma_{90}(\hat{\varphi}_{90}) \geq \Gamma_{45}(\hat{\varphi}_{45}) \\ \hat{\varphi}_{45} & \text{if } \Gamma_{90}(\hat{\varphi}_{90}) < \Gamma_{45}(\hat{\varphi}_{45}) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

IV. MEASUREMENTS

In order to verify the accuracy of the proposed algorithm, we have measured twelve ESPAR antenna radiation patterns associated with twelve main beam directions for two elevation angles considered in the paper, namely $\theta_{90} = 90^\circ$ and $\theta_{45} = 45^\circ$. The measurements took place in our $11.9 \times 5.6 \times 6.0$ m anechoic chamber at 2.484 GHz with horizontal resolution equal to 1° .

After the calibration phase, a signal generator (within NI PXIe-5840 Vector Signal Transceiver), placed in the same anechoic chamber 8.0 m from the ESPAR antenna, has been used to generate 10 dBm 2.484 GHz BPSK test signal impinging the antenna. The same NI PXIe-5840 unit has been connected to ESPAR antenna's output in order to record RSS values of the test signal received by the antenna. For every

RSS measurement, 10 snapshots were generated and additive white Gaussian noise has been added to the received signal to generate signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) equal to 20dB.

Signal's directions were chosen by rotating the receiving ESPAR antenna with a discreet angular step equal to 5° in the horizontal plane. Such measurements were performed for 7 elevation angles $\theta_t \in \{90^\circ, 80^\circ, 70^\circ, 60^\circ, 50^\circ, 40^\circ, 30^\circ, 20^\circ\}$. In consequence, 72 test directions $\varphi_t \in \{0^\circ, 5^\circ, \dots, 355^\circ\}$ were obtained for each elevation angle θ_t . For every elevation angle θ_t and for every horizontal signal's direction φ_t , twelve RSS values has been recorded for all the main beam antenna configurations. Estimation errors calculated for $\theta_t = 90^\circ$ and $\theta_t = 60^\circ$ using standard PPCC estimator (1) and radiation patterns measured in the $\theta_{90} = 90^\circ$ plane only are shown in Fig. F1, while in table T1 one can find estimation error mean, root-mean-square (RMS) error, standard deviation and precision calculated for all 7 elevation angles θ_t .

Fig. F1. DoA estimation errors for the standard PPCC estimator and ESPAR antenna's radiation patterns measured in the $\theta_{90} = 90^\circ$ plane obtained for the elevation angles $\theta_t = 90^\circ$ and $\theta_t = 60^\circ$. RMS error value calculated for the 72 test directions in the horizontal plane equals to 2,004° and 2,375° correspondingly (see text for explanations).

TABLE T1
DOA ESTIMATION ERRORS CALCULATED FOR 7 ELEVATION ANGLES USING STANDARD PPCC ALGORITHM AND ESPAR ANTENNA'S RADIATION PATTERNS MEASURED IN THE $\theta_{90} = 90^\circ$ PLANE (SEE TEXT FOR EXPLANATIONS)

θ_t	mean	rms	std	precision
90	1,653°	2,004°	1,140°	4°
80	1,375°	1,752°	1,093°	4°
70	1,556°	1,826°	0,963°	4°
60	1,833°	2,375°	1,520°	7°
50	1,764°	2,300°	1,497°	6°
40	2,458°	3,147°	1,978°	9°
30	3,458°	4,794°	3,344°	13°
20	3,333°	4,200°	2,573°	12°

The results in table T1 clearly indicate that for decreasing elevation angles θ_t the overall accuracy gradually deteriorates as RMS errors and corresponding precision associated with DoA estimation increase. To this end, ESPAR antenna's radiation patterns measured in $\theta_{90} = 90^\circ$ and $\theta_{45} = 45^\circ$ elevation planes during the initial calibration

phase have been used to calculate estimators $\Gamma_{90}(\varphi)$ and $\Gamma_{45}(\varphi)$ defined by (2) and (3). Then, the unknown DoA angles $\hat{\varphi}$ have been obtained for every elevation angle θ_t and for every horizontal signal's direction φ_t using (4).

The results gathered in table T2 and in Fig. F2 indicate that using the proposed modification of the PPCC method one can increase the DoA estimation accuracy. In the original PPCC method, RMS value and precision stay at the similar level for elevation planes ranging from $\theta = 90^\circ$ to only $\theta = 70^\circ$, while the proposed modification doubles this elevation angles span. Because the improved PPCC algorithm exhibits acceptable errors for lower elevation angles, it can successfully be applied in practical WSN deployment scenarios involving differences in heights of WSN nodes installed within the environment.

TABLE T2

DOA ESTIMATION ERRORS CALCULATED FOR 7 ELEVATION ANGLES USING THE MODIFIED PPCC ALGORITHM AND ESPAR ANTENNA'S RADIATION PATTERNS MEASURED IN TWO HORIZONTAL PLANES ($\theta_{90} = 90^\circ$ AND $\theta_{45} = 45^\circ$) (SEE TEXT FOR EXPLANATIONS)

θ_t	mean	rms	std	precision
90	1,653°	2,004°	1,140°	4°
80	1,375°	1,752°	1,093°	4°
70	1,556°	1,803°	0,918°	4°
60	1,542°	1,904°	1,125°	4°
50	1,097°	1,409°	0,891°	4°
40	2,028°	2,723°	1,831°	7°
30	3,417°	4,726°	3,288°	13°
20	3,222°	4,150°	2,634°	9°

Fig. F2. RMS error values for the standard PPCC estimator and its proposed modification employing ESPAR antenna's radiation patterns measurements in two elevation planes during the calibration phase (see text for explanations).

V. CONCLUSIONS

In the article, we propose a modification of PPCC algorithm used in DoA estimations based on RSS values recorded at ESPAR antenna's output port. The modification allows one perform the algorithm's calibration using ESPAR antenna's radiation patterns at two different elevation planes, which improves PPCC-based DoA estimation accuracy. Measurements of the ESPAR antenna prototype performed in

our anechoic chamber indicate that, for the proposed PPCC algorithm modification, it is possible to estimate DoA of a signal impinging the antenna with similar RMS errors and precisions in elevation planes from $\theta = 90^\circ$ to $\theta = 50^\circ$. This doubles the original PPCC method's elevation span ranging from $\theta = 90^\circ$ to only $\theta = 70^\circ$. In consequence, the proposed method can successfully be used within WSN nodes equipped in ESPAR antennas to provide DoA estimation functionality in WSN setups, that involve differences in heights of WSN nodes installed in the environment.

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